

Reactions of IRRI strains to gall midge at Chiplima, India

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Eight advanced International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) rice strains and 64 strains of Indian origin were subjected

to a gall-midge resistance varietal trial at the Regional Research Station of Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology during 1975 and 1976 in the main crop season (May to November). The silver shoot count revealed that none of the IRRI lines had absolute resistance, but when compared with the susceptible check Jaya, each showed a certain degree of resistance (see table). ❧

Yields and silver shoot (ss) count of IRRI cultivars, 1975 and 1976 main crop seasons. Chiplima, India.

Cultivar	Ss (no./sq m)		Yield (kg/ha)	
	1975	1976	1975	1976
IR2071-621-2-3	29	0	1749	3030
IR2071-636-5-2-6	14	0	2726	2479
IR2070-414-3-9	16	28	720	3305
IR2070-439-6-5	2	25	1955	3030
IR2070-464-1-3-6	5	11	4012	2823
IR2070-471-2-5	50	0	1749	2410
IR2071-213-6-6	108	77	1235	2617
IR2071-486-9-2	13	11	3292	2823
RPW 6-13 (Resistant check)	5	56	1646	1377
Jaya (Susceptible check)	163	95	1235	413

seedlings are transplanted in July or August. Short-duration varieties are grown in the uplands and the long-duration varieties elsewhere. Tall indigenous types withstand drought stress more or less in the uplands, but are usually poor yielders; many recent high yielding varieties are drought susceptible.

A number of suitable upland rice varieties from the International Rice Upland Rice Nursery in 1976 at Bankura and Purulia were identified. Seeds of 185 types were drilled at two sites in June 1976. Twenty-five local entries were added at Bankura. Growth, effect of drought stress, and other factors were recorded periodically during frequent, prolonged periods of rainless days. About 50% of the entries were credited with acceptable tolerance for drought. Some promising types are listed in the table. ❧

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Adverse soils

Breeding for adverse-soils tolerance

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In densely populated South and Southeast Asia, 100 M ha suited to rice lie idle largely because of soil toxicities (Table 1). Also, on about 50 M ha of cultivated land, deficiencies of zinc, phosphorus, or iron, or excesses of iron, aluminum, or manganese limit rice yields.

In 1976 the International Rice Research Institute screened cultivars from its germ plasm bank, evaluated promising lines, and tested the progeny from its hybridization program for tolerance of adverse soil conditions (Table 2).

Table 1. Problem rice soils (current and potential) of South and Southeast Asia.

Kind of soil	Extent (M ha)
Saline soils	62.5
Alkali soils	2.2
Acid sulfate soils	9.8
Organic soils	29.0

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Drought tolerance

Upland rice varieties for drought-prone areas of West Bengal, India

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Rice that depends solely on rainfall occupies about 69% of the rice land in Bankura district and 86% in Purulia

district in West Bengal, India. Short and badly distributed rainfall, undulating land, and poor soil-moisture retention are chiefly responsible for frequent drought. In 1976 rice experienced its most severe drought of recent times.

Seed is usually sown with the onset of the southwest monsoon in June (monsoon lasts until September), and

Promising upland rice varieties for drought-prone areas of West Bengal, India.

Name	Source	Duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)
Se. 322 B.19	Senegal	91	4.44
IRAT 10	Ivory Coast	92	4.10
IET 1444	India	105	3.88
B.9c-Md-3-3	Indonesia	105	3.84
Brown Gora	India	92	3.60
DV 110	Bangladesh	106	3.50
DZ 41		91	3.48
ARC 7060	India	92	3.28
IET 3226		100	3.23
C22	IRRI	118	3.20
B.541 c/km/19/3/4	Indonesia	118	3.20
Se. 319 G.	Senegal	89	3.19
IR2035-227-1	IRRI	119	3.08
Aus 8	Bangladesh	114	3.00